

SOiLO-LiVE

SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY
OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES

D7.9

Report on workshop program

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Executive Summary

This report covers the workshops held between January 2023 and December 2024.

These workshops are part of WP7 (Outreach, dissemination and communications), are held in different municipalities of the oil mills that have signed up to the sustainability protocol, are open to anyone who wishes to attend, and aim to disseminate and train farmers in different sustainable practices, focusing on those that promote healthy olive soil and raise awareness of the SOIL O-LIVE project.

The conference is divided into four parts: in the first, Deoleo technicians present the sustainability protocol, providing training on practices covering social, economic, environmental and quality aspects.

The second part deals with the SOIL O-LIVE project and the results obtained in each phase, as well as possible tools or methods that can be implemented in olive groves. This part is given by the SOIL O-LIVE coordinator or prominent members of the consortium, who are not only able to present the project but are also experts in sustainable practices applicable to olive groves.

This is followed by a third part in which farmers are trained on an aspect or topic related to sustainability that is particularly relevant and important in the area where the conference is held. This part is taught by local technicians or experts in the subject matter.

Finally, there is an open question and answer session to discuss the different topics covered during the day.

Below is a summary of the workshops held in 2023 and 2024.

1. Workshops Soil O-live 2023

During 2023, active work has been done on the project, with **17 workshops** held in different locations in **Andalusia and Extremadura**, with the active participation of **595 farmers**.

These Workshops have been taught by the Deoleo technical team, mills technical team and with the collaboration of other members of Soil O-live. Also highlight the work carried out in dissemination by both the Deoleo Communication team and Hermes Communication.

Some of these events have had media coverage in regional media such as Canal Sur, Día de Córdoba, ABC, etc.

Workshop 2023	PICTURE	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA OLIVARERA DE LUCENA, Lucena (Córdoba) 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA SAN MARCOS, BEAS DE SEGURA (Jaén) 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR, BENATAE, (Jaén) 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA SAN BLAS, SORIHUELA DEL GUADALIMAR, (Jaén) 		

- **SCA SANTA MARINA DE AGUAS SANTAS, FERNAN NUÑEZ (Córdoba)**

- **SCA LA UNIÓN DE CHILLUEVAR (Chilluevar, Jaén)**

- **SCA JESÚS NAZARENO, BUJALANCE, (Córdoba)**

- **SCA SAN FRANCISCO, VILLANUEVA DEL ARZOBISPO (JAÉN)**

- **SCA SAN ISIDRO DE LOJA, (Loja, Granada)**

- **SCA SAN ISIDRO, IZNATORAF (JAÉN)**

- **SCA SAN GINES Y SAN ISIDRO, (Sabiote, Jaén)**

- **SCA OLEICOLA BAEZA (Baeza, Jaén)**

- **ALMAZARAS DE LA SUBBETICA, (Carcabuey, Córdoba)**

- **SOCIEDAD COOPERATIVA VIÑAOLIVA, (Almendralejo, Badajoz)**

- **SCA OLEOCAMPO, (Torredelcampo, Jaén)**

- **SCA NTRA SRA DE LOS REMEDIOS, (Jimena, Jaén)**

- **S.COOP VIRGEN DE LA ESTRELLA,
(Los Santos de Maimona, Badajoz)**

Grupo	LUGAR DE REALIZACIÓN	FECHA
Jaencoop	SCA SAN MARCOS, BEAS DE SEGURA (JAÉN)	11/04/2023
	SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR DE BENATAE (JAÉN)	12/04/2023
	SCA SAN BLAS, SORIHUELA DEL GUADALIMAR (JAEN)	24/04/2023
	SCA LA UNION DE CHILLUEVAR, (JAÉN)	02/05/2023
	SCA SAN FRANCISCO, VILLANUEVA DEL ARZOBISPO (JAÉN)	16/05/2023
	SCA SAN ISIDRO, IZNATORAF (JAÉN)	30/05/2023
Almaliva	OLIVARERA DE LUCENA, LUCENA (CÓRDOBA)	01/02/2023
	SCA SAN ISIDRO DE LOJA, GRANADA	19/05/2023
	SCA JESUS NAZARENO, BUJALANCE, CÓRDOBA	03/05/2023
	SCA SANTA MARINA DE AGUAS SANTAS, FERNAN NUÑEZ, CÓRDOBA	27/04/2023
	ALMAZARAS DE LA SUBBETICA, CARCABUEY, CÓRDOBA	14/06/2023
Viñaoliva	VIÑAOLIVA, ALMENDRALEJO, BADAJOZ	12/09/2023
	S.COOP VIRGEN DE LA ESTRELLA, LOS SANTOS DE MAIMONA, BADAJOZ	20/10/2023
InterOleo	SCA SAN GINES Y SAN ISIDRO, SABIOTE, JAÉN	01/06/2023
	SCA OLEOCAMPO, TORREDELCAMPO, JAÉN	21/09/2023
	SCA OLEICOLA BAEZA, BAEZA, JAÉN	08/06/2023
	SCA NTRA SRA DE LOS REMEDIOS, JIMENA, JAÉN	27/09/2023

2. Workshops Soil O-live 2024

During this year 2024, we have been proactively working on the design of a calendar, where farmers were informed of the dates of the next days and encouraged to sustainable practices through famous phrases each month. The presentation of the calendar and training agenda was presented on March 7, 2024.

Around 300 calendar units have been distributed among our farmers who have joined the sustainability project..

During this year 2023, active work has been carried out on the project, with the holding of **14 workshops** in different locations in Andalusia, Extremadura and Portugal, with the active participation of more than 300 farmers.

In addition to participating in some additional events, such as collaboration with CETAEX of Extremadura, collaboration with the Jaencoop group in a reforestation where children participated, or collaboration with the Tierra Creativa foundation in a sustainability event in the municipality of Villanueva de Córdoba.

WORKSHOP 2024	PICTURE
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NTRA SRA DE LA SALUD, (Castro del Río, Córdoba) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA OLIVARERA Y CEREALISTA SAN SEBASTIAN (San Sebastián de los Ballesteros, Córdoba) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA OLIVARERA LOS PEDROCHES (Pozoblanco, Córdoba) 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SCA BEDMARENSE (Bedmar, Jaén) 	

- **SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADROR DE CANENA (Canena, Jaén)**

- **SCA LA UNIÓN DE BUJALANCE (Bujalance, Córdoba)**

- **SCA SAN JUAN DE LA CRUZ, (Beas de Segura, Jaén)**

- **SCA SAN JUAN BAUTISTA, (Peñolite, Jaén)**

- **NTRA SRA DE GUADALUPE, (Úbeda, Jaén)**

- **SCA VERA CRUZ, (Villanueva del arzobispo, Jaén)**

- **LAGAR DO SOBRADO, (Ferreira do Alentejo Portugal)**

- **ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS, (Sierra de Yeguas, Málaga)**

- **S.COOP SAN ISIDRO,
(Villafranca de los Barros,
Badajoz)**

GROUP	PLACE	DATE
JAENCOOP	SCA VERA CRUZ, VVA	09/04/2024
ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS	SCA ACEITES DE SIERRA DE YEGUAS	11/04/2024
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN JUAN DE LA CRUZ, BEAS DE SEGURA	16/04/2024
JAENCOOP	SCA SAN JUAN BAUTISTA, PEÑOLITE	18/04/2024
JAENCOOP	SCA NTRA SRA DE GUADALUPE, UBEDA	24/04/2024
MOLINO DEL GENIL	LAGAR DO SOBRADO, PORTUGAL	08/05/2024
ALMALIVA	NTRA SRA DEL ROSARIO, NUEVA CARTEYA	09/05/2024
ALMALIVA	SCA OLIVARERA DE LOS PEDROCHES,	16/05/2024
INTEROLEO	SCA SAN ISIDRO LABRADOR DE CANENA,	27/05/2024
INTEROLEO	SCA BEDMARENSE	17/09/2024
VIÑAOLIVA	ASAMBLEA S.COOP VILLAFRANCA DE LOS BARROS	18/09/2024
INTEROLEO	SCA LA UNION DE BUJALANCE	25/09/2024
ALMALIVA	SCA OLIVARERA Y CEREALISTA SAN SEBASTIAN,	26/09/2024
ALMALIVA	SCA NTRA SRA DE LA SALUD, CASTRO DEL RIO	23/10/2024